

REPORT:

*A1.1.5: Communication report on
the definition of flow control
concepts, terms and components
used in microfluidics and related
database*

Work package 1

This report was written as part of activity A 1.1.5 from the EMPIR Establishing Metrology Standards in Microfluidic Devices (MFMET) project. The three-year European project commenced on 1st June 2021 and focused on providing a generic methodology of accurate measurement of a particular quantity in a microfluidic device by utilising standardised methods and reference documents, e.g. VIM & GUM. For more details about this project, please visit www.mfmet.eu

The help from the members of the Microfluidics Association (www.microfluidics-association.org) is greatly acknowledged.

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The EMPIR initiative is co-funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the EMPIR Participating States

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1. Scope

This document provides a compilation of basic and general concepts and associated terms related to flow control whose definitions are currently lacking harmonisation. A proposal of definitions and symbols has been produced as well as a Vocabulary of Flow Control (containing terms such as repeatability, stability, settling time, liquid properties, dead volume, volume dispensed, accuracy, range, etc). This compilation is drawn on existing symbols and standards for flow control.

Activity number	Activity description	Partners (Lead in bold)
A1.1.5 M16	INESC MN with support from IPQ, CETIAT, DTI, RISE, HSG-IMIT and BHT will compile the information acquired in A1.1.2-A1.1.4 into a communication report on the definition of flow control concepts, terms and components used in microfluidics and related database. This communication report will be disseminated to the standardisation organisations ISO/TC48/WG3 and WG5, ISO/TC229 and CEN/TC332/WG7.	INESC MN , IPQ, CETIAT, DTI, HSG-IMIT, BHT, RISE

2. Introduction

Flow control is a critical aspect of microfluidics, as it enables the precise manipulation of fluids in microchannels. Applications using flow in microchannels are technologies such as inkjet printing, continuous flow polymerase chain reaction (PCR) for diagnosis of infectious diseases, microscale systems for total analysis systems (microTAS), and organ-on-a-chip for drug trials. The flow control concepts, terms, and components used in microfluidics are diverse and complex, and understanding these concepts is essential for designing and optimizing microfluidic systems. With this communication report we aim to provide a comprehensive overview of the flow control concepts, terms, and components used in microfluidics, as well as a related database to facilitate communication and understanding among researchers, engineers, and technicians in the field.

Elements to have in mind when preparing this document are in MFMET Reports A1.1.1 Literature and market research: definitions, characteristics, specifications, application and function of flow control components [1] and A1.1.2 Definitions Symbols and Vocabulary of Flow Control [2], and these elements are:

1. **Definitions:** Definitions of key terms related to flow control in microfluidics.
2. **Components:** Lists of key components used in microfluidics, including microfluidic chips, pumps, sensors, and actuators.
3. **Concepts:** Overviews of key flow control concepts, including flow rate, flow control, pressure control, flow direction, and flow pattern.
4. **Applications:** Examples of applications of flow control in microfluidics, including biomedical research, environmental monitoring, and industrial processing.

3. Definition of Flow Control Concepts

Flow control concepts in microfluidics refer to the principles and techniques used to regulate and manage the flow of fluids within microfluidic systems. The components presented here

are some of those identified in A1.1.1 Literature and market research: definitions, characteristics, specifications, application and function of flow control components [1] and A1.1.2 Definitions Symbols and Vocabulary of Flow Control [2] and submitted to ISO/TC 48/WG 3 Microfluidic Devices to be considered in the review of ISO 10991:2023 Microfluidics Vocabulary [3]. Some of the key flow control concepts include:

1. **Flow Rate:** Quantity of fluid which passes through a given area per unit time. Flow rate can be expressed in mass or volume units per time units.
2. **Flow Stability:** Standard deviation of the flow rate. Notes: depends on the number of points and time window for which the measurements were carried out. The flow stability of a device can change depending on the application and other parameters fluctuations such as standard stable conditions (e.g. pressure and temperature of the fluid and/or of the ambient conditions).
3. **Internal Volume:** Maximal total available volume comprised within a fluidic component, device, or system under normal atmospheric pressure. The internal volume is the sum of the swept and dead volumes, [$\mu\text{L}/\text{mm}^3/\text{m}^3$].
4. **Hydrodynamic resistance:** Ratio of pressure drop over flow rate for a certain component or system. Expressed as pressure units over flow rate units.
5. **Pressure drop:** Difference of pressure between two positions in the flow path. Expressed in pressure units [Pa].

4. Related Database

To facilitate communication and understanding among researchers, engineers, and technicians in the field, we have developed a database with an inventory for 5 classes of flow control components (Flow generation, Flow measurement, Pressure measurement, Manual dispensers and Valves, Flow control components and accessories) (Figure 1, [4]). The database intends to present the flow control components along with information such as basic operating principles, family of components and types and subtypes of components. It is a goal of the database to create an interactive and efficient overview of information on flow control components.

Figure 1: Overview of the design of the database. Notice the database has five classes: flow generator, flow sensor, pressure sensor, manual dispensers and valves, and finally flow control components and accessories. Each class has a tree structure of properties and sub properties. All classes have similar structure and fields for harmonization.

The Database is being populated by Project partners and stakeholders. The information is accessible to the public in the format of a CSV file, which can easily be turned into a table as in Figure 2:

MFMET Database for Flow Control Components

<https://voda.teknologisk.dk/MFMET-database/>

Flow generator	Type	Flow range	Flow stability	Flow unit	Pressure range	Pressure unit	Connection size	Connection unit	Manufacturer	Model	Connection type
Peristaltic pumps	39.6	63600	1.98	3180	ml/h	-	-	-	Watson Marlow	403U/R1	-
Peristaltic pumps	9601	980	48	99	ml/h	-	-	-	SK mMedical	SK600III	-
Peristaltic pumps	1.2	66	-	-	ml/h	-	-	-	Aquatech Co	RP-Q1.2N-P202-DC3V	-
Peristaltic pumps	1.8	740	-	-	ml/h	-	-	-	Sartorius	Masterflex Economy Drive	-
Peristaltic pumps	9	102000	-	-	µl/h	-	-	-	Jobst Technology	CPP-1 pump family	-
Piezo electric or diaphragm pump	0.3	480	-	-	ml/h	-	-	-	Bartels	MP 6	-
Piezo electric or diaphragm pump	0	180	-	-	ml/h	-	-	-	Takasago	SDMP302	-
Piezo electric or diaphragm pump	0	420	-	-	ml/h	-	-	-	Takasago	SDMP306	-
Piezo electric or diaphragm pump	-	-	-	-	nl/h	-	-	-	TTP Ventus	LT Series Micropumps	-
Pressure driven pump	-	-	-	-	nl/h	0	2	bar	Fluigent	MFC5A, C series	-
Pressure driven pump	-	-	-	-	nl/h	0	0.2	bar	Elveflow	OB1	-
Pressure driven pump	-	-	-	-	nl/h	0	2	bar	Festo	VPPM series	-
Pressure driven pump	-	-	-	-	nl/h	0	0.2	bar	Elveflow	AF1 100	-
Pressure driven pump	-	-	-	-	nl/h	0	0.75	bar	Biophysical Tools	VS-750	-
Pressure driven pump	-	-	-	-	nl/h	0	0.5	bar	Blacktrace (Dolomite)	Mitos Fluida Pump	-
Pressure driven pump	-	-	-	-	nl/h	0	0.345	bar	Fluigent	Flow EZ LU-FE2-0345	-
Syringe pump	50	9000000	-	-	µl/h	-	-	bar	Tecan	Cavro XLP 6000	Tubing fitting
Syringe pump	0.01359	69660	0.0001359	696.6	µl/h	-	-	bar	New Era	NE-1002X	Luer
Syringe pump	1	1000	-	-	µl/h	-	-	bar	Tecan	Cavro Centris	Tubing fitting
Syringe pump	0.0001	90000	0	0.0035	µl/h	0	500	kPa	Chemxy	Nexus 3000	Tube
Syringe pump	0.00048	5000	-	-	µl/h	0	10	bar	Cetoni	Nemesys	Tube
Syringe pump	0.48	3.6	-	-	nl/h	0	10	bar	Cetoni	Nemesys 5	28UNF female
Syringe pump	0.72	30000000	0.00252	105000	nl/h	-	-	bar	Nexus	Nexus 3000	-
Syringe pump	9.6	198	0.192	3.96	ml/h	-	-	bar	BBraun	Perfusor Compact 5	-
Syringe pump	9.6	999	0.192	19.98	ml/h	-	-	bar	BBraun	PerfusorSpace	-
Syringe pump	0.0006	5400	0.000006	54	ml/h	-	-	bar	KR Analytical	Fusion	-
Syringe pump	0.6	5296800	0.003	26484	ml/h	-	-	bar	Kid Scientific	Legato 100	-
Syringe pump	96	960	1.92	19.2	ml/h	-	-	bar	SK Medical	SK500I	-
Syringe pump	0.0006	2100	0.000006	21	ml/h	-	-	bar	New Era	NE 1000	-
Syringe pump	0.6	13249200	0.0021	46372.2	nl/h	-	-	bar	Harvard Apparatus	PHD 22/2000	-
Syringe pump	0.0007	31257	0.01	0.01	ml/h	-	-	bar	New Era Pump Systems, Inc	NE-300	-
Syringe pump	0.0007	31699	0.01	0.01	ml/h	-	-	bar	New Era Pump Systems, Inc	NE-1000	-
Syringe pump	0.00143	66023	0.01	0.01	ml/h	-	-	bar	New Era Pump Systems, Inc	NE-4000	-
Syringe pump	0.0004	5153.2	0.01	0.01	ml/h	-	-	bar	New Era Pump Systems, Inc	NE-1200	-
Syringe pump	7.56E-08	1561.2	0.005	0.005	ml/h	-	-	bar	Harvard Apparatus	PROG. DUAL	-

Flow sensor											
Type	Flow range	Flow stability	Flow unit	Pressure range	Pressure unit	Connection size	Connection unit	Manufacturer	Model	Connection type	
Coriolis mass flow meter	0 30	-	kg/h	0 200	bar	6	mm	Bronkhorst	M14-AGD-22-0-s	Swagelok	
Coriolis mass flow meter	0 2	-	kg/h	0 200	bar	6	mm	Bronkhorst	M13-AGD-22-0-2	Swagelok	
Coriolis mass flow meter	0.05 200	0.4 0.4	g/h	-	bar	-	-	Bronkhorst	Mini CORI-FLOW ML120	-	
Differential pressure flow sensor	60 12000	0.3 60	µL/h	-	bar	-	-	Seyonic	MEMS flow meter	-	
Other technology for flow measurement in microfluidics	-	-	nL/h	6 89	bar	-	-	Omega	PX481A-100GSV	-	
Thermal sensor	0 3000	-	µL/h	0 50	bar	1/16"	inch	Sensision	SU-0430	-	
Thermal sensor	0 99.6	-	mL/h	-	bar	-	-	Sensision	LD20-2600B	-	
Thermal sensor	90 300000	4.5 15000	µL/h	-	bar	-	-	Elveflow	Microfluidic flow sensor - MFS	-	
Thermal sensor	0.005 2	0.0001 0.0001	g/h	-	bar	-	-	Bronkhorst	µ-FLOW	-	
Thermal sensor	30 360	0.05 10.8	mL/h	-	bar	-	-	Siargo	LF6000	-	
Thermal sensor	0 0.09	0.001 0.001	mL/h	-	bar	-	-	Flugent	FLOW UNIT FLU-XS	-	

Pressure sensor											
Type	Flow range	Flow stability	Flow unit	Pressure range	Pressure unit	Connection size	Connection unit	Manufacturer	Model	Connection type	
Other technology for pressure measurement	-	-	nL/h	-0.066 0.2	bar	-	-	PendoTECH	Single-use pressure sensor	-	
Other technology for pressure measurement	-	-	nL/h	-0.76 4.14	bar	-	-	SciLog	SciPres	-	
Other technology for pressure measurement	-	-	nL/h	-0.066 0.4	bar	-	-	Edwards Lifescience	True Wave	-	
Other technology for pressure measurement	-	-	nL/h	0 16	bar	-	-	Elveflow	Microfluidic inline pressure sensor - MFP	-	
Other technology for pressure measurement	-	-	nL/h	0 5	psi	5.1	mm	Honeywell	24PC 4CF6D	-	

Manual dispensers and valves											
Type	Flow range	Flow stability	Flow unit	Pressure range	Pressure unit	Connection size	Connection unit	Manufacturer	Model	Connection type	
Blister	50 50	-	mL	-	bar	-	-	Aradigm	blister	-	
Blister	85 100	-	mL	-	bar	-	-	Captite	reservoir	-	
Blister	5 1,000	-	mL	-	bar	-	-	Celula	blister	-	
Blister	-	-	nL/h	-	bar	-	-	Curetis	integrated prefilled reservoirs	-	
Blister	180 180	-	mL	-	bar	-	-	Daktari	blister (developed by ThinXX)	-	
Blister	1,500 1,500	-	mL	-	bar	-	-	Elveflow	reservoir	-	
Blister	50 1,000	-	mL	-	bar	-	-	Hahn-Schickard	blister	-	
Blister	15 45	-	mL	-	bar	-	-	Medical System for Industry	pouch	-	
Blister	500 4,500	-	mL	-	bar	-	-	microfluidicsChipShop	reservoir	-	
Blister	25 1,000	-	mL	-	bar	-	-	microfluidicsChipShop	blister	-	
Blister	150 5,000	-	mL	-	bar	-	-	ThinXX	blister	-	
Blister	-	-	nL/h	-	bar	-	-	ThinXX	reagent plug	-	
Fully integrated valves	-	-	nL/h	-	bar	-	-	Fluidigm	Nanoflex valves	-	
Pipette	0.2 10000	-	µL/h	-	Pa	-	-	Sartorius	Picus	Tip	
Pipette	1 20	-	mL	-	bar	-	-	Eppendorf, Gilson, Sartorius, Mettler, Biohit, VWR, Brand, Thermofisher, Socorex	Fixed pipette	-	
Pipette	0.1 20	-	mL	-	bar	-	-	Eppendorf, Gilson, Sartorius, Mettler, Biohit, VWR, Brand, Thermofisher, Socorex	Variable pipette	-	
Pipette	0.2 10	-	mL	-	bar	-	-	Sartorius, Brand, Oxford	Digital pipette	-	
Pipette	0.001 0.01	-	mL	-	bar	-	-	Socorex	ACURA 825.0010Y	-	
Pipette	0.01 0.1	-	mL	-	bar	-	-	Sartorius	Biohit MLINE 725050	-	
Pipette	0.002 0.02	-	mL	-	bar	-	-	Sartorius	Biohit MLINE 725030	-	
Pipette	0.005 0.05	-	mL	-	bar	-	-	Sartorius	Proline Plus 728040	-	
Pipette	0.005 0.05	-	mL	-	bar	-	-	Jeancons	Sealette 3902A	-	
Pipette	1 5	-	mL	-	bar	-	-	Sartorius	Biohit Proline 720110	-	
Pipette	0.02 0.2	-	mL	-	bar	-	-	Sartorius	Biohit Proline 720070	-	
Pipette	0.2 1	-	mL	-	bar	-	-	Sartorius	Biohit Proline BH-1000/200	-	
Pipette	0.0001 0.0025	-	mL	-	bar	-	-	Sartorius	Biohit Proline 720010	-	
Pipette	0.002 0.02	-	mL	-	bar	-	-	Edvotek	589-1	-	
Standalone valve (Pieze, SMA, MEMS, ect.)	0 0	-	nL/h	0 172	bar	6	mm	Swagelok	SS-430X54	Swagelok	
Standalone valve (Pieze, SMA, MEMS, ect.)	0 0	-	nL/h	0 172	bar	6	mm	Swagelok	SS-42C54	Swagelok	
Standalone valve (Pieze, SMA, MEMS, ect.)	-	-	nL/h	-	bar	-	-	Gyger AG	SMLD 300G	-	
Standalone valve (Pieze, SMA, MEMS, ect.)	-	-	nL/h	-	bar	-	-	Lee	VHS	-	
Standalone valve (Pieze, SMA, MEMS, ect.)	-	-	nL/h	-	bar	-	-	Takasago	NV-2-MFF (Diaphragm Isolation Valves)	-	
Standalone valve (Pieze, SMA, MEMS, ect.)	-	-	nL/h	-	bar	-	-	Takasago	EXAK Series (Diaphragm Isolation Valves)	-	
Standalone valve (Pieze, SMA, MEMS, ect.)	-	-	nL/h	-	bar	-	-	Brükert	2/2 Way Microfluidic Whisper Valve Type 6712	-	
Standalone valve (Pieze, SMA, MEMS, ect.)	-	-	nL/h	-	bar	-	-	Elveflow	LVF-MFV-NP-22-NC_2	-	
Standalone valve (Pieze, SMA, MEMS, ect.)	-	-	nL/h	-	bar	-	-	Actuator Solution	SMA valve	-	
Standalone valve (Pieze, SMA, MEMS, ect.)	-	-	nL/h	-	bar	-	-	Bistable micro valve	Memetis	-	
Standalone valve (Pieze, SMA, MEMS, ect.)	-	-	nL/h	-	bar	-	-	Bartels	SMV 2/2 NC Active Valve	-	
Standalone valve (Pieze, SMA, MEMS, ect.)	-	-	nL/h	1 72	bar	-	-	BIO-CHEM	100PD3MP12-01SM	-	

Flow control components and accessories											
Type	Flow range	Flow stability	Flow unit	Pressure range	Pressure unit	Connection size	Connection unit	Manufacturer	Model	Connection type	
Flow generator connector	-	-	nl/h	0.95	6	bar	6	mm	Festo	QSM-6	Pneumatic connection
Flow generator connector	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	-	-	Instech	SC20/12	
Flow generator connector	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	0.812	mm	Instech	SC20/15	
Flow generator connector	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	0.644	mm	Instech	SC22/15	
Flow generator connector	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	25ga x 12mm	mm	Instech	SC25/12	Coupler
Flow generator connector	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	22ga x 8mm	mm	Instech	SC22/8	Coupler
Flow generator connector	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	22ga x 12mm	mm	Instech	SC22/12	coupler
Flow generator connector	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	1/32"	inch	BIO-CHEM	Pinch Valve Y Connectors Y-01P	pinch valve
Nozzle	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	27 ga x 1.2"	inch	Instech	Luer Stub (LS27K)	Luer Stub
Nozzle	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	1.024	mm	Instech	Luer Stub (LS18K)	Luer stub
Nozzle	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	25 ga x 1.2"	inch	Instech	Luer Stub (LS25K)	Luer stub
Nozzle	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	0.812	mm	Instech	Luer Stub (LS20K)	Luer stub
Nozzle	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	21 ga x 1/2"	inch	Instech	Luer Stub (LS21)	Luer stub
Nozzle	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	22ga x 15mm	mm	Instech	Right Angle Coupler (SC22/15RA)	right angle coupler
Nozzle	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	0.644	mm	Instech	Luer Stub (LS22K)	
Nozzle	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	0.25mm (316) x 5mm	mm	BD Medical	Needle BD Thin Wall 5mm CNP-6998412	
Reservoir	-	-	mL	-	-	Pa	2.5	mm	Terumo Syringe	SS*02LE1 Luer Lock tip	
Reservoir	1	1	-	-	-	Pa	-	-	Terumo Syringe	U-100 Insulin	
Reservoir	1	1	-	-	-	bar	-	-	Terumo Syringe	SS+01H1	
Reservoir	1	2	-	-	-	bar	-	-	Terumo Syringe	BS-025 6% Luer	
Reservoir	1	24	-	-	-	bar	-	-	Henkesasswolf	NORM-JECT 4200-X00V0	
Reservoir	1	10	-	-	-	bar	-	-	Dispomed	ECOJECTA® - Einmalspritzen 20010	
Reservoir	1	20	-	-	-	bar	-	-	Dispomed	ECOJECTA® - Einmalspritzen 20020	
Reservoir	1	50	-	-	-	bar	-	-	Normax	Syringe RUTHE luer lock 50 ml (4.6030006)	
Reservoir	1	5	-	-	-	bar	-	-	Normax	Syringe RUTHE luer lock 5 ml (4.6000003L)	
Reservoir	1	2	-	-	-	bar	-	-	Normax	Syringe RUTHE luer lock 2 ml (4.6030001L)	
Reservoir	1	1	-	-	-	bar	-	-	Normax	Syringe RUTHE luer lock 1 ml (4.6030000L)	
Tubing	-	-	nl/h	0	24	bar	6	mm	RS PRO	483-4970	Tube
Tubing	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	1/16"	inch	Supelco	Stainless Steel Tubing Kits	Tubing
Tubing	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	1/16"	inch	Aline	Silicone tubing	hose barb
Tubing	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	1.6	mm	Dolomite	PTFE tubing	Dolomite connectors
Tubing	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	1.6	mm	Fulgent	PEEK tubing	Luer
Tubing	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	0.36	mm	labsmith	Fused Silicon	Luer
Tubing	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	1	mm	microfluidicChipShop	PTFE tubing	(mini)Luer
Tubing	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	1.6	mm	Micronit	Teflon tubing	nuts and ferrules
Tubing	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	3	mm	Thinxx	Silicone tubing	(mini)Luer
Tubing	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	1	mm	Deutsch & Neumann	N/A	
Tubing	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	0.51	mm	Freudenberg Medical Europe	N/A	
Tubing	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	0.6858	mm	Instech	BPU-T35	
Tubing	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	0.58	mm	Instech	8TPE-50	
Tubing	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	0.76	mm	Instech	8TPE-60	
Tubing	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	0.86	mm	Instech	8TPE-90	
Tubing	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	0.812	mm	Instech	BTCEX-22	
Tubing	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	0.46 x 0.91 mm x 30 m	mm	Instech	8TPE-25	
Tubing	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	0.63 x 1.40mm x 30 m	mm	Instech	0.63 x 1.40mm x 30 m	
Tubing	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	0.63 x 1.40mm x 30 m	mm	Instech	VAHBPU-T22	
Tubing	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	0.76 mm I.D. / 1.65 mm O.D.	mm	HelixMark	60-011-04 standard silicone tubing	
Tubing	-	-	nl/h	-	-	bar	1.6 mm / 2.2 mm / 300 mm	mm	SIM	A072-171 PTFE Tubing	

Figure 2: Output table from the MFMET Database.

An additional document to facilitate the comparison of flow control components was developed and reported into A1.1.4 Generic specification list for comparison of flow control components [5]. Part of the information collected was sent to ISO/TC 48/WG 3 Microfluidic devices to initiate the process of submission of a Technical Specification to support the comparison of Microfluidic Pumps: ISO/TS 6417 Microfluidic pumps — Symbols and performance communication [6].

5. Conclusion

The definition of flow control concepts, terms, and components used in microfluidics is essential for facilitating communication and understanding among researchers, engineers, and technicians in the field. This report provides a short overview of these concepts, terms, and components, as well as a related database to facilitate communication and understanding.

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